

Overall study design

Title of the study	In vivo metastasis modeling and CRISPR screens reveal polyunsaturated-lipids supporting extravasation and colonization in metastasis		
Document creation date	06/09/2024	Corresponding Email	zouyilong@westlake.edu.cn
Principle investigator	Yilong Zou	Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Untargeted
Institution	Westlake University	Clinical	Yes

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	2-phase system	2-phase system	MTBE
Derivatization	-	Were internal standards added prior extraction?	Yes
pH adjustment	None		

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Ammonium acetate, Formic acid	MS Level	MS2
Number of separation dimensions	One dimension	Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	1.5
Separation type 1	LC	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS2	High resolution
Separation mode 1 (liquid)	RP	Resolution at m/z 200 at MS2	30000
Detector	Mass spectrometer	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS2	5
MS type	Orbitrap	Recording mode of raw data at MS2	Profile mode
MS vendor	Thermo	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No
Ion source	ESI		

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Quality control	Yes
Type of Blanks	Extraction blank, Solvent blank	Type of QC sample	Sample pool

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	No
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Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Yes	Summary data	Quantification and identification data
Link to repository / ID to entry	included as supplementary dataset	Raw data upload	Available on request
Are metadata available?	Available on request	Additional comments	-

Sample Descriptions

patient-derived primary ovarian cancer cell / Human / Tissues (e.g., liver, heart, brain)

Perfusion	No	Additives	CryoStor® cell cryopreservation media, Merck, C2999
Provided information	Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Were samples stored under inert gas?	Yes
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Additional preservation methods	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Biobank samples	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Sample homogenization	Yes
Storage time (month)	8	Sample homogenization solvent	Tumor Dissociation Kit, human, miltenyi, 130-095-929
Freeze-thaw cycles	1		

xenograft-derived ES-2-GFP-Luc cells / Mouse / Tissues (e.g., liver, heart, brain)

Perfusion	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Provided information	-	Additional preservation methods	No
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Biobank samples	No
Instant sample preparation	Yes	Sample homogenization	Yes
Storage temperature	4-8 °C	Sample homogenization solvent	Tumor Dissociation Kit, human, miltenyi, 130-095-929
Additives	None		

cultured human cancer cell / Human / Cells

Provided information	-	Additives	None
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	Yes	Additional preservation methods	No
Storage temperature	4-8 °C	Biobank samples	No

cultured mouse cancer cell / Mouse / Cells

Provided information	-	Additives	None
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Storage temperature	4-8 °C	Biobank samples	No

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	TG	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipidSearch
Fragment name			
FA1-OH			
FA2-OH			
FA3-OH			
MG1-OH			
MG2-OH			
MG3-OH			
NL(FA1-H+NH4)			
NL(FA2-H+NH4)			
NL(FA3-H+NH4)			
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	Yes		

1) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

2) PC[M+HCOO]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of negative (precursor) ion	[M+HCOO] ⁻	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipidSearch
Fragment name			
M-CH3			
FA1-H			
FA2-H			
M-FA1-FA2+H2O-CH3			
(P-Cho)-CH3-H			
GP-H3O			
LPC(FA1)-CH3			
LPC(FA2)-CH3			
LPA(FA1)-H3O			
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	Yes		

2) PC[M+HCOO]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

3) PC O[M+HCOO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC O	Limit of detection	S/N ratio
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	No
Identification level	Molecular species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+HCOO]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipidSearch
Fragment name			
M-CH3			
FA2-H			
M-FA1-FA2+H2O-CH3			
(P-Cho)-CH3-H			
LPC(FA1)-CH3			
LPA(FA1)-H3O			
FA2-H-COO			
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Data manipulation	-
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	Yes		

3) PC O[M+HCOO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

4) PE[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE	Limit of detection	S/N ratio												
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	No												
Identification level	Molecular species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No												
Polarity mode	Negative	Model for separation prediction	Yes												
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-												
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipidSearch												
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Fragment name</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>FA1-H</td></tr> <tr><td>FA2-H</td></tr> <tr><td>M-FA1-FA2+H2O-H</td></tr> <tr><td>GP-H3O</td></tr> <tr><td>PH(Ethanolamine)-H</td></tr> <tr><td>FA2-H-COO</td></tr> <tr><td>LPA(FA1)-H3O</td></tr> <tr><td>LPE(FA1)-H3O</td></tr> <tr><td>LPE(FA1)-H</td></tr> <tr><td>LPE(FA2)-H</td></tr> <tr><td>LPE(FA2)-H3O</td></tr> </tbody> </table>				Fragment name	FA1-H	FA2-H	M-FA1-FA2+H2O-H	GP-H3O	PH(Ethanolamine)-H	FA2-H-COO	LPA(FA1)-H3O	LPE(FA1)-H3O	LPE(FA1)-H	LPE(FA2)-H	LPE(FA2)-H3O
Fragment name															
FA1-H															
FA2-H															
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Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Data manipulation	-												
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes												
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes												
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-												
Check isomer overlap	Yes														

4) PE[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

5) PE O[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE O	Limit of detection	S/N ratio							
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	No							
Identification level	Molecular species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No							
Polarity mode	Negative	Model for separation prediction	Yes							
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-							
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipidSearch							
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Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Data manipulation	-							
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes							
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes							
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-							
Check isomer overlap	Yes									

5) PE O[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

6) PE P[M+H]+ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE P	Limit of detection	S/N ratio						
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	No						
Identification level	Molecular species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No						
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes						
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H]+	Additional dimension/techniques	-						
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	LipidSearch						
<table border="1"> <tr> <th>Fragment name</th> </tr> <tr> <td>NL(PE)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>LPE(FA1)+H</td> </tr> <tr> <td>LPE(FA1)-OH</td> </tr> <tr> <td>MG(FA2)-OH</td> </tr> <tr> <td>M-FA2-(CH2=COHCH2OH)</td> </tr> </table>				Fragment name	NL(PE)	LPE(FA1)+H	LPE(FA1)-OH	MG(FA2)-OH	M-FA2-(CH2=COHCH2OH)
Fragment name									
NL(PE)									
LPE(FA1)+H									
LPE(FA1)-OH									
MG(FA2)-OH									
M-FA2-(CH2=COHCH2OH)									
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Data manipulation	-						
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes						
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes						
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-						
Check isomer overlap	Yes								

6) PE P[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-